

DEVELOPMENT OF ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION AWARENESS' PROGRAM FOR B, ED STUDENT TEACHERS

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Introduction

India is one of the few countries of the world that have made a specific references in the constitution to the satisfy for the need of environmental protection and improvement. The Provision of environmental protection in Indian constitutions Article 32,48a, 51a, 226, and 253, so we think this questions and giving answers by implementation of Education. What is .sustainable development goals 2030? Importance of Environmental Education in school curriculum and Teacher Education? What is. Environmental Education? Why its need? How to implementation in Education?

Environment Education helps students understand how their decisions and actions affect the environment, builds knowledge and skills necessary to address complex environmental issues, as well as ways we can take action to keep our environment healthy and sustainable for the future. Environmental awareness skills development is a part of sustainable development and also Life skills Education. Its including in self-awareness one of the Life skills. Environmental Education. as a process to promote to awareness and understanding of the environment, its relationships with man and his activities .It is also aimed at developing responsible actions necessary for preservation, conservation and improvement of the environment and its components Awareness of Environment al Education is the Education that connected with the Environment it also demonstrates what we can do. It is the education not merely through book and lectures but education through direct exposure to the environment, learning by doing, exploring and problem solving

Environmental Skills are social skills and they are directed towards personal actions or actions towards others. Its empowering individual to interact with the self as well as others and develop healthy lifestyle and responsive and responsible behaviour.

Teachers need to Development of self-Environmental Awareness' and express effectively information or thought using to their students written verbal or visual medium in teaching learning process . It is also to develop capacity of understanding current environmental problems and prevention effectively. So it's essential to a special training for student teacher .so researcher prepare a "Development of Environmental Education Awareness program' for B, Ed student teachers."

Objectives of the study:

1. To develop an 'Environmental Education Awareness' program for B. Ed student teachers.
2. To study the effectiveness of the Environmental Education Awareness' 'Program.

Operational definitions of the terms:

1. B,Ed Student teachers.: All the students enrolled for B. Ed. course. Present study 40 students enrolled to B. Ed. Course 2015-16 of S.N.D.T. college of Education for women Pune.

2. Environmental Education Awareness:

Environmental Education Awareness means to develop capacity of understanding current environmental problems and prevention. To express effectively information or thought using written verbal or visual medium. It will be measured in terms of qualitative analysis on test of Environmental Education Awareness to develop by the researcher Acquisitions of Environmental skills measured in terms of aggregate score obtained by.

3. Environmental Education Awareness' program

A Special program developed by the researcher to impart Environmental Education amongst the B,Ed student teachers. Total duration of the program of 7 clock hours in which 3 hours was Theoretical orientation of given through worksheets and printed self-learning material. 4 hours assigned to practical work.

4. Effectiveness:-

The positive difference in the qualitative analysis of B,Ed student teachers .on pre-test and post-test about Environmental Education Awareness' developed by the researcher.

Research Hypotheses:

There will be positive and significant difference in pre-test and post-test mean scores of B, Ed student teachers after implementation 'Environmental Education Awareness Program.

1. Null Hypotheses:

There would be no positive and significant difference in pre-test and post-test mean scores of B.Ed. student teachers after implementation of 'Environmental Education Awareness Program.

Significance of the present study:

Globalization has brought new life style and technology leading to destruction of environment. Students must be aware of protection of environment. Skills are sensitized students about the environment issues for human existence and sustainable development

Higher levels of environmental knowledge correlate significantly with a higher degree of pro-environment and conservation behaviour. The more people know, the more likely they are to recycle, be energy efficient, conserve water, etc.

Environment Education helps students understand how their decisions and actions affect the environment, builds knowledge and skills necessary to address complex environmental issues, as well as ways we can take action to keep our environment healthy and sustainable for the future.

Environmental education connects us to the world around us, teaching us about both natural and built environments. Environment Education raises awareness of issues impacting the environment upon which we all depend, as well as actions we can take to improve and sustain it.

Whether we bring nature into the classroom, take students outside to learn, or find impromptu teachable moments on a nature walk with our families, Environmental Education has many benefits for youth, educators, schools, and communities.so researcher decided to development

environmental awareness program for B.Ed. student teachers and studied it's also analysed . So researcher prepare a program and implemented

A special program of 7 clock hour was developed by the researcher to impart amongst them. Theoretical orientation of Environmental Education Awareness Was given 3hours through printed self-learning material and the practical's provided practice for B, Ed student teachers applying skills during teaching and interactions with students in school environments in simulated condition. Hence the study will be useful for teacher, prospective researcher, and other professionals.

Scope and limitations of the study:

- 1) Present study included training program including for B, Ed student teachers
- 2) Duration of the Environmental Education Awareness' 'program was 7 clock hours in which 3urs were assigned to practical work. Theoretical orientation of Environmental Education Awareness Program was given through worksheets and printed self-learning material.
- 3) The Sample was included sample including only female students.
- 4) Data collection tools were not standardized but were prepared by researcher.

There will be limitations to broader generalizations of the conclusions due to incidental sample including only female students and non-standardized tools prepared by researcher.

Method of Research: The experimental method was used suitable to objectives of the study.

Experimental Design: Single group pretest post design was used.

Variables in the research:

1. Independent Variable:

A for the B,Ed student teachers of secondary level Environmental Education Awareness Program developed by the researcher.

2. Dependent Variable:-

An aggregate score of on the tests of B,Ed student teachers

3. Controlled Variable:-

The pretest and post tests on Environmental Education Awareness test developed by the researcher were parallel, and were administered with uniform procedure by the researcher.

Sample:

Incidental sampling was used. All the 52 students enrolled for B. Ed. course in S.N.D.T. College of Education Pune, were included.

Tools used for data collection:

Environmental Education Awareness test Measurement tool was developed by the researcher.

A feedback questioner

Tools used data for analysis:

Qualitative analysis: open responses on training program, Environmental Education Awareness test and feedback questioner were analysed qualitatively.

Implementation of the Environmental Education Awareness program:

Environmental Education Awareness program was prepared by the researcher based on. Environmental Education Awareness program for sustainable development was of 7 hours, which

included various activities related to the role of teacher in educational transaction. Along with this some conceptual and application activities and learning experiences were also organized. Methods and techniques was used Role play, game and simulation, pair and share, group discussion etc. Its implemented very interactive and interesting .Implementation of program was useful of B.Ed student teachers

Experiment and Implementation:

The study was conducted on the student teachers from S. N. D.T. College of Education, Pune.

Analysis and Interpretation of data Presentation of data:

1. Interpretation of Data:

From the observation of Environmental Education Awareness test Measurement in Post-test are higher than that of pre-test scores. Score is increased.

All students' scores on Environmental Education Awareness test measurement tests were increasing of the Environmental Education Awareness education program developed by the researcher.

Testing of Hypothesis:

1. Research hypotheses:

There will be positive and significant difference in Environmental Education Awareness test Measurement pre-test and post-test scores of B, Ed student teachers implementation of 'Environmental Education Awareness program.

This positive research hypothesis was converted into Null hypotheses for testing.

2. Null Hypothesis:

There would be no positive and significant difference in Environmental Education Awareness test Measurement pre-test and post-test of B,Ed student teachers after implementation of Hence Null hypothesis is rejected and research hypothesis is accepted. The score on Environmental Education Awareness Measurement post-test is higher than pre-test of the B,Ed student teachers. Hence, the program was developed by researcher was significantly increased of B,Ed student teachers.

3. Qualitative analysis:

Qualitative analysis on the basis of open responses of the question in Environmental Education Awareness test, selected activities of self-learning material in teaching program and open responses of feedback questionnaire.

Responses of the training program feedback questionnaire of the B,Ed student teachers

On the various activities included in the training program were analysed qualitatively. One Example of Responses of would be teachers of sample. One of the activity given by researcher for would be teachers. Would teachers responses given by would be teachers.-

Benefits of Environmental Education program

Imagination and enthusiasm are heightened

Learning transcends the classroom

Critical and creative thinking skills are enhanced

Tolerance and understanding are supported

Biphobia and nature deficit disorder decline

State and national learning standards are met for multiple subjects

Communities are strengthened

Healthy lifestyles are encouraged Responsible action is taken to better the environment

Students and teachers are empowered

Responsible action is taken to better the environment

Students and teachers are strong aware socially, economically

The post-test means score of Environment awareness skills Measurement of student teachers is found significantly higher than that of pre-test mean score. That means Environment awareness skills education program prepared by the researcher based on Environmental awareness skills developed this program B.Ed. Student Teachers.

Open responses of post-test are qualitatively better as compared to responses on pretest regarding fluency, flexibility and originality. Hence the Environmental awareness skills Education Program implemented by the researcher has prove to be effective for developing Higher order thinking , critical thinking ,creative thinking , design making and collaborative and cooperative skills

Hence Environmental skills Education Program developed by the researcher proved to be effective for developing, Environmental awareness skills.

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